

A pipeline for the discovery of causal variants in Mendelian diseases

Paolo Maccallini

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1 Introduction

Whole-exome sequencing (WES) has become a pivotal tool in diagnosing Mendelian disorders, offering a diagnostic yield ranging from 25–40%, depending on the phenotype and setting, in cohorts of subjects with suspected rare genetic disorders. Whole-genome sequencing (WGS) increases the diagnostic rate of about 5–20% when performed after nondiagnostic WES (1). Approximately 5–20% of individuals with Mendelian disorders have a clinically relevant structural variant (SV), detected either by WES or by WGS (2). These results suggest starting with the analysis of SNVs/indels by WES and then extending the analysis to WGS and SVs if unsuccessful. It should also be noted that WES usually has a greater depth than WGS, leading to a more confident variant calling.

2 Methods

2.1 DNA sequencing, raw reads alignment, and variant calling

Whole genome sequencing was performed by DanteLabs, with DNA sequencing conducted on paired-end libraries generated from extracted genomic DNA. Sequencing was carried out on Illumina's NovaSeq™ 6000 System at an average read depth of 30. Alignment of the raw reads was achieved using the DRAGEN Bio-IT platform, with mappings aligned to both GRCh37 and GRCh38 human reference genomes.

The same raw reads were aligned using GATK best practices workflows on the platform Terra (3), a cloud environment that offers virtual machines with optimised GATK installation, and ready-to-use genetic pipelines written in Workflow Development Language (WDL) (4). In particular, paired FASTQ files were converted into unmapped BAM (uBAM) format using the BAM-To-Unmapped-BAM workflow, from the workspace Sequence-Format-Conversion (5). Conversion from uBAM to BAM format was performed using workflow Preprocessing-For-Variant_Discovery-HG38 of workspace GATK4-Germline-Preprocessing-VariantCalling-JointCalling (6).

Workflow Haplotypecaller-HG38, from the same workspace, generated a gVCF for each family member. Next, workflows Generate-Sample-Map and Joint-Genotyping were applied to the four files to build the final gVCF, including the four samples of the pedigree, plus 50 samples from the 1000 Genomes Project (7), required by the workflow for joint variant calling optimisation (4).

For each one of the four samples in the pedigree, the workflow gatk-sv-single-sample of workspace GATK-Structural-Variant-Single-Sample was employed (8). The four VCF files were then combined using the command merge of BCFtools (9) (see par. 2.4). Structural variants were then added to the gVCF containing SNVs and indels using the R package vcfR (10) and a custom script. The result of all these analyses is file FAM_NuMa_GRCh38.vcf.gz of Table 10. This file was used as input for a standalone Exomiser local installation, while a file with structural variants only was used in PerGen.

2.2 PerGen pipeline

2.2.1 Prioritization of SNVs and Indels by Seqr

The Terra environment offers the possibility to upload a gVCF generated by GATK workflows to Seqr, a web-based tool that performs annotation and filtering based on in silico filters (CADD, SIFT, Eigen, and many more), inheritance patterns, functional annotation, quality and allele balance. It also provides interactive panels to explore the available literature and data on genes and variants of interest (11). Seqr is fast and versatile, with an intuitive interface. At the date of writing, it does not offer the possibility to parse structural variants.

I submitted to Seqr file FAM_NuMa_GRCh38 before the SVs were added. Then I launched a search with the settings indicated in Table 1. When using the setting “any affected”, any variant with at least one alternative allele in the affected individual is collected. In this search, the genotype of the unaffected individuals is not taken into account. This search includes exomic regions, regulatory regions, and splice regions. To minimize the number of variants in the output, I set as a filter a score greater than zero for Eigen, one of the available in silico predictors of pathogenicity. Eigen is an ensemble method that can be used for both coding and non-coding variants. It considers several computational scores, like SIFT, Pholy-Phen, Mutation Assessor, PhyloPri, PhyloPla, PhyloVer, and others; it also considers the frequency of the variants and other parameters. This method produces estimates of predictive accuracy for each functional annotation score and then uses them to weight each score and calculate a meta score as a weighted linear combination of individual associations (12). Importantly, given the fact that it uses several parameters, it can give a score even when single methods (like VEST3 or SIFT) do not have a score, which makes it useful for coding variants, too. The recommended threshold for functional consequences is ≥ 0 , according to (13).

Saved search	De Novo/Dominant Permissive			
Inheritance	Any Affected	TSAA8269	Unaffected	-
		TSAA1992	Affected	1-2
		TSAB3094	Unaffected	-
		TSAB3137	Unaffected	-
Pathogenicity	Default settings			
Annotation	Default settings, but SpliceAI > 0.5			
In Silico Filters	Eigen > 0			
Frequency	AF < 0.01, seqr AF < 1			
Location	See Table 2			
Call Quality	Affected only, Show All Variants, Genotype Quality > 30, Allele Balance > 10			

Table 1. Settings for Seqr search.

Since Seqr allows downloading only for searches with no more than 1000 variants, and our search selects 2223 candidate variants, I split it into five, as indicated in Table 2. The genetic coordinates of the chromosomes refer to genome assembly GRCh38.p14 (14). This generates five files that were downloaded for further analysis. The five files were then read and merged by PerGen.R, a custom R script written in R 4.1.1 (15) and run on RStudio 2024.09.0+394 (16).

2.2.2 Further annotation and filtering with a custom R script

In the autosomes of a typical exome/genome, the percentage of heterozygous calls is about 60%. In the absence of the genomes/exomes of the parents, many heterozygous variants can emerge from the

prioritization process of the proband NGS. But only the subset included in genes in which it is sufficient a broken copy to manifest the phenotype must be taken into account. To address this problem, PerGen.R retrieve and adds to each gene (identified by NCBI ID) its probability of haploinsufficiency and triplosensitivity, as calculated in (17). Probabilities were downloaded from Zenodo (18), at record 6347673 and gene symbols were converted into NCBI ID employing the package rentrez for NCBI eUtils API interrogation (19). Also, the DOMINO score (20), a probability of dominant pattern of inheritance, was added to each gene. DOMINO calculates the probability that a gene has a dominant inheritance pattern by taking into account 432 features. It was trained on 985 genes and, when tested on 99 genes, showed an area under the curve of 0.92. The result of DOMINO is given as a Probability of being an Autosomal Disease (PAD) (20).

File name	Location	N. variants
DeNovoDominat_permissive_1.txt	1:1-248956422 2:1-242193529 3:1-198295559 4:1-190214555 5:1-181538259	701
DeNovoDominat_permissive_2.txt	6:1-170805979 7:1-159345973 8:1-145138636 9:1-138394717 10:1-133797422	465
DeNovoDominat_permissive_3.txt	11:1-135086622 12:1-133275309 13:1-114364328 14:1-107043718 15:1-101991189	455
DeNovoDominat_permissive_4.txt	16:1-90338345 17:1-83257441 18:1-80373285 19:1-58617616 20:1-64444167	458
DeNovoDominat_permissive_5.txt	21:1-46709983 22:1-50818468 X:1-156040895 Y:1-57227415 M:1-16569	144
		2223

Table 2. Locations and number of variants for Seqr searches.

To further characterize variants potentially involved in regulatory activity, the scripts search for matches in the RegulomeDB file for the corresponding genome build. RegulomeDB integrates data from GWAS results on noncoding regions, regulatory regions classified by the ENCODE Project (which provides a map of open chromatin and protein binding regions), manually curated loci known to be involved in regulatory functions, and loci that explain variation in expression level of mRNA, known as Expression Quantitative Trait Loci (eQTLs) (21). The categories included in RegulomeDB are summarized in Table 3. Note that the lower the score, the more likely the position involvement in gene regulation is. The scores are attributed to coordinates of a single base; therefore, in the case of deletions, my script selects the lowest score that falls within its length.

For the annotation of variants included in non-coding RNA stretches, I used the ncRNAVAR database, which collects 4238 associations between variants in human ncRNA regions and traits. These associations have been manually curated (22). The coordinates are provided with respect to GRCh38, but rsids are included in the ncRNAVAR file too.

For each variant included in the Seqr output, the Combined Annotation Dependent Depletion (CADD) PHRED score was added, using the latest version available for build GRCh38 (GRCh38-v.1.7, at time of writing). Seqr provides CADD scoring in its output, too, but I noticed that it does not match with the latest version, and I assume that version v1.6 is employed by Seqr for GRCh38. Another note is that the CADD API does not provide annotations for indels. Therefore, I decided not to use it, but to submit a VCF file to the web-based tool instead. CADD is a tool for assigning to each human variant a score of deleteriousness (called C-score) based on the fate that a variant has been subjected to during human evolution from the common primate ancestor: those alleles that have been depleted in their frequency are likely to have been discarded by the pressure of selection because they tend to decrease the fitness of carriers. CADD algorithm compares the frequency of the alleles of each known human variant with both the genetic material belonging to the inferred human-chimpanzee ancestral genome and a simulation for random genetic events (23). The meaning of a C-score is as follows: if a variant has a C-score of x then, defined the value $p = 10^{-\frac{x}{10}}$, we have that the variant is included among the pN_{tot} most deleterious variants, where N_{tot} is the total number of variants considered (~8.6 billion). As an example, if the score is 10, then the variant is among the 10% of N_{tot} with the highest level of deleteriousness; if the score is 20, then we have $p = 10^{-2}$ and the variant is included among the 1% of N_{tot} with the highest level of deleteriousness. And so forth. It must be added that the C-score we have here described is the scaled C-score, also designated as PHRED.

Category		Description
Likely to affect binding and linked to expression of a gene target	1a	eQTL + TF binding + matched TF motif + matched DNase footprint + DNase peak
	1b	eQTL + TF binding + any motif + DNase footprint + DNase peak
	1c	eQTL + TF binding + matched TF motif + DNase peak
	1d	eQTL + TF binding + any motif + DNase peak
	1e	eQTL + TF binding + matched TF motif
	1f	eQTL + TF binding/DNase peak
Likely to affect binding	2a	TF binding + matched TF motif + matched DNase footprint + DNase peak
	2b	TF binding + any motif + DNase footprint + DNase peak
	2c	TF binding + matched TF motif + DNase peak
Less likely to affect binding	3a	TF binding + any motif + DNase peak
	3b	TF binding + matched TF motif
Minimal binding evidence	4	TF binding + DNase peak
	5	TF binding or DNase peak
	6	Motif hit
	7	Other

Table 3. The categories that RegulomeDB classifies the positions into. I have copied the table from Table 2 of (21).

The score calculated by AMELIE based on the HPO terms list, and the relevant literature was added to each gene. AMELIE (Automatic Mendelian Literature Evaluation) is a computational tool designed to prioritize and annotate genes associated with rare Mendelian diseases. By leveraging machine

learning and extensive biomedical literature, AMELIE scores candidate genes based on phenotypic similarity to known disease-associated genes (24). In this pipeline, AMELIE is accessed via its API.

Symptom	HPO ID
Arachnoid cyst	HP:0100702
Asthenia	HP:0025406
Brain fog	HP:0033630
Chronic fatigue	HP:0012432
Cognitive fatigue	HP:0033236
Dust mite allergy	HP:0410324
Elevated circulating hepatic transaminase concentration	HP:0002910
Elevated circulating neuron-specific enolase concentration	HP:4000189
Empty sella turcica	HP:6000483
Exercise-induced muscle fatigue	HP:0009020
Fatigue	HP:0012378
Hepatic steatosis	HP:0001397
Hypermetropia	HP:0000540
Increased circulating IgE concentration	HP:0003212
Increased circulating IgG4 level	HP:0032300
Increased theta frequency activity in EEG	HP:0031535
Increased muscle fatiguability	HP:0003750
Mitral valve prolapse	HP:0001634
Orthostatic hypotension	HP:0001278
Orthostatic tachycardia	HP:0012173
Papillary thyroid carcinoma	HP:0002895
Scoliosis	HP:0002650
Temporal lobe dysplasia	HP:0034222
Urinary retention	HP:0000016
Young adult onset	HP:0011462

Table 4. Description of the phenotype of the proband by HPO terms.

2.2.3 Phenotype description and gene lists

To characterize the genotype of the proband, Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) terms were retrieved from the HPO database (25). These terms were used to generate a targeted gene list for annotating variants from the pipeline by accessing the HPO annotation dataset in an automated fashion at <https://hpo.jax.org/data/annotations>. This service provides manually curated phenotype-genotype associations. The complete phenotype of the proband is indicated in Table 4, but different subsets of the HPO terms were input into the pipeline, as specified below. The number of HPO terms improves the performance of tools for variant prioritization based on phenotype annotation, and more than five HPO terms are recommended (26).

2.2.4 Exomiser

The output of Seqr is used to generate a VCF file, which is submitted to a local installation of Exomiser, a tool for genome-wide prioritization of genomic variants, including non-coding and regulatory variants, based on patient phenotypes to differentiate candidate genes. To perform an analysis, Exomiser requires the patient's genome or exome in VCF format and their phenotype encoded in HPO terms. Exomiser can also analyze trios or small family genomes, provided a pedigree file in PED format is included (as specified in the distribution README).

The application of Exomiser to 4,877 Mendelian diseases with a known molecular diagnosis demonstrated that the algorithm identified the causal variant among the top candidate genes in 82.6% of cases, within the top three in 91.3%, the top five in 92.4%, and the top ten in 93.6% of cases. Notably, performance was not reduced in the absence of family members (singletons), which accounted for 1,591 of the 4,877 probands (27).

Exomiser offers three scores: a variant score, a phenotype score, and a combined score. It offers a rank for the variants, too. The recommended thresholds are collected in Table 5.

	Variant score	Phenotype score	Combined score	Rank
Description	From allele frequency and pathogenicity, variant level	From phenotypic similarity (humans, animals), gene level	Phenotypic similarity and pathogenicity, gene level	Based on the combined score
Cut-off	≥ 0.8	≥ 0.6	≥ 0.7	≤ 5
Sensitivity	80%	60%	89%	92%
Precision	15%	15%	15%	18%

Table 5. Precision and sensitivity of the three Exomiser scores for specific thresholds, according to (27).

In this context, precision is the number of causal variants selected, divided by the total number of variants selected, considering the entire pool of patients. Recall (or sensitivity) is the number of causal variants selected divided by all the causal variants (27). Rank is based on the combined score, which is calculated from the variant and the phenotype score (28).

The local installation of Exomiser employed in this study consists of release 14.0.0 with data version 2406 and ReMM.v0.3.1, executed on an HP Z4 G4 workstation with an Intel Xeon W-2123 processor, 64 GB of RAM, running Windows 11. Exomiser is executed within the R script with the function `system()`, after generation of a custom phenopacket file including the HPO terms selected from the ones in Table 4. The analysis was conducted according to the YAML file indicated in Table 6. The phenotype is passed to Exomiser with a YAML file like the one in Table 7.

```
analysis:
inheritanceModes: {}
  inheritanceModes: {
    AUTOSOMAL_DOMINANT: 0.1,
    AUTOSOMAL_RECESSIVE_HOM_ALT: 0.1,
    AUTOSOMAL_RECESSIVE_COMP_HET: 2.0,
    X_DOMINANT: 0.1,
    X_RECESSIVE_HOM_ALT: 0.1,
```

```

X_RECESSIVE_COMP_HET: 2.0,
MITOCHONDRIAL: 0.2
}
analysisMode: PASS_ONLY
frequencySources: [
  THOUSAND_GENOMES,
  TOPMED,
  UK10K,
  GNOMAD_E_AFR,
  GNOMAD_E_AMR,
  GNOMAD_E_EAS,
  GNOMAD_E_NFE,
  GNOMAD_E_SAS,
  GNOMAD_G_AFR,
  GNOMAD_G_AMR,
  GNOMAD_G_EAS,
  GNOMAD_G_NFE,
  GNOMAD_G_SAS
]
pathogenicitySources: [ REVEL, MVP, REMM ]
steps: [
  hiPhivePrioritiser: { },
  priorityScoreFilter: { priorityType: HIPHIVE_PRIORITY, minPriorityScore: 0.501 },
  failedVariantFilter: { },
  regulatoryFeatureFilter: { },
  frequencyFilter: { maxFrequency: 2.0 },
  pathogenicityFilter: { keepNonPathogenic: true },
  inheritanceFilter: { },
  omimPrioritiser: { }
]

```

Table 6. The content of the YML file used for genomic analysis in the Exomiser executions of this study.

The Regulatory Mendelian Mutation (ReMM) score employed by Exomiser for genome analysis is a supervised machine learning method trained on about 14 million human non-coding variants (on both GRCh37 and GRCh38), of which only about 400 are known pathogenic mutations. This score aims to detect possible pathogenic SNVs in non-coding regions of WGS from patients suspected of Mendelian diseases (29).

```

---
id: TSAA1992
subject:
id: TSAA1992
sex: MALE
phenotypicFeatures:
- type:
  id: HP:0100702
  label: Arachnoid cyst
- type:
  id: HP:0025406
  label: Asthenia
- type:

```

```

id: HP:0033630
label: Brain fog
- type:
id: HP:0012432
label: Chronic fatigue
- type:
id: HP:0033236
label: Cognitive fatigue
- type:
id: HP:0001278
label: Orthostatic hypotension
- type:
id: HP:0012173
label: Orthostatic tachycardia
- type:
id: HP:0011462
label: Young adult onset
htsFiles:
- uri: C:/Users/macpa/OneDrive/Appunti/Genetics/Mendelian Fatigue/mydata/FAM_NuMa_GRCh38.vcf.gz
htsFormat: VCF
genomeAssembly: hg38
metaData:
created: '2024-11-19T09:39:21Z'
createdBy: macpa
resources:
- id: hp
name: human phenotype ontology
url: http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/hp.owl
version: hp/releases/2024-08-13
namespacePrefix: HP
iriPrefix: 'http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/HP_'
phenopacketSchemaVersion: 1.0

```

Table 7. Example of YML file used to pass to Exomiser the phenotypic description of the proband.

Method	Threshold	Specificity (%)	Sensitivity (%)	Reference
CADD	> 20	59.99	94.18	(13)
Eigen	> 0	62.88	92.64	(13)
PolyPhen	> 0.453	56.58	92.02	(13)
SIFT	≤ 0.05	67.9	86.36	(13)
REVEL	≥ 0.4	85.27	83.33	(13)

Table 8. Performances of the computational methods evaluated in (13) on a dataset of missense variants retrieved from ClinVar. The thresholds are the ones proposed by the dbNSFP database, ANNOVAR, or the original studies, for distinguishing deleterious nsSNVs.

2.2.5 Search for pathogenic SNVs and indels

The Exomiser scores (variant score, gene score, and combined score) are added as further annotation to the variants, then pathogenic variants (according to ClinVar classification) are saved before filtering. Missense variants are selected and filtered using in silico the pathogenicity scores PolyPhen,

SIFT, and REVEL, with the thresholds collected in Table 8, where I also reported performances in terms of sensitivity and specificity as calculated by a benchmark analysis on known pathogenic and benign variants (13).

All frameshift and nonsense variants are retained. Variants in splice regions are filtered using spliceAI, with a threshold of 0.5. SpliceAI is a deep learning-based tool developed to predict the impact of genetic variants on RNA splicing. It assigns scores to variants, indicating the likelihood that a given mutation will disrupt normal splicing patterns. These scores range from 0 to 1, with higher scores suggesting a greater probability of splicing alteration (30). Variants predicted to have regulatory features by RegulomeDB and variants included in ncRNAVAR are retained. All the remaining variants are filtered with CADD and Eigen, with the thresholds collected in Table 8.

2.2.6 Family filtering of SNVs and indels

For the autosomal dominant pattern of inheritance, PerGen searches for variants that are autosomal or pseudoautosomal, where all the relatives are homozygous for the reference allele, and where at least one of the following conditions is fulfilled: DOMINO probability above 0.5, haploinsufficiency probability above 0.5, autosomal dominant mode of inheritance predicted by Exomiser.

For the autosomal recessive mode of inheritance, autosomal and pseudoautosomal variants are kept when only the proband is homozygous recessive or when the proband is heterozygous for two variants harboured by the same gene (manual verification of the absence of this same phenotype in any of the relatives is required).

For X-linked inheritance, considering that the proband is a male, variants on the X chromosome that do not fall within the pseudoautosomal regions are scrutinized: only variants present in the proband that are absent in the male relative and that are at most heterozygous in the female relatives, are kept (manual verification that compound heterozygosity is not present in female relatives is required).

2.2.7 Structural variants with Exomiser

The pipeline read a gVCF including structural variants of the four family members, plus 154 other healthy individuals from the 1000 Genomes Project (file FAM_NuMa_GRCh38_SV_bcftools_TOT of Table 10). It then merges this file with a VCF file, including only the SNVs and indels that survived all the previous filtering steps. These variants must be added to account for cases of compound heterozygosity where a structural variant is in trans with an SNV/indel. This file was then input to the Exomiser for genomic analysis with a PED file built so that the 154 unrelated individuals are included in the same family as the proband with unaffected status and unknown sex, to maximise the number of variants removed by family filtering. Domino probability and dosage sensitivity are added as described for SNVs/indels.

2.2.8 GeneMatcher

GeneMatcher is a web-based repository where mutations found in a specific patient can be uploaded, along with the phenotype. Researchers around the world can search for patients with similar phenotypes and mutations (matches), and they can decide to contact each other to share their results for mutual advantage (31). The service is available at: <https://genematcher.org/>. An API is also available, with the same functionalities as the website. Note, though, that Gene Matcher does not implement HPO codes for phenotype description, and it might be necessary to first manually set the submission, using their interface for phenotype description, and then the API can be used to add genes

and/or variants to the existing submission. Significant variant and a complete phenotypic description of the proband were added manually to the GeneMatcher website, in search of similar cases.

2.2.9 Prioritization of SVs with AnnotSV

AnnotSV is a software tool designed for the annotation and prioritization of structural variants. It integrates data from numerous sources, including ClinVar, gnomAD-SV, DECIPHER, OMIM, and ExAC. These include population frequencies, clinical annotations, dosage sensitivity scores, overlapping known pathogenic or benign variants, and potential gene impacts. It is available as a standalone installation and as a web-based service (32-34).

In this pipeline, AnnotSV is employed to reduce the number of structural variants by removing the common ones. I uploaded file TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra_SV_TOT.bed to the web-based service, selected the reference genome GRCh38, indicated the number of the column including the SV type (column 5 in our case), indicated the number of the column including the name of the samples (column 6 in our case), raised the AF threshold for SVs to 0.05. No HPO list was provided. I then downloaded the output in TSV format and gave it the name TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra_AnnotSV.tsv. Structural variants were then prioritized using the following criteria:

- ACGM class ≥ 3 or not available (3 = US, 4 = LP, 5 = P);
- AF < 0.05 on gnomAD;
- AF $< 0.05 + \phi_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{0.05(1-0.05)}{2 \cdot 157}}$ on whole sample;

The second cut-off for AF in whole sample is calculated by considering the upper limit of the 95% confidence interval of the 0.05 cutoff, as a correction for the small sample considered (157 individuals, for $2 \cdot 157$ alleles. Where $\phi_{1-\frac{\alpha}{2}} = 1.96$ is the value of a standard normal random variable greater than 97.5% of the corresponding distribution, with $\alpha = 0.05$.

2.3 Analysis of mitochondrial DNA

Mitochondrial variants were extracted from the WGS of the proband and aligned to GRCh37 (the reference genome for the mitochondrial chromosome is rCRS). A custom script selected variants with depth above 5 and filter status equal to PASS. Variants with heteroplasmy below 0.2 were removed. Then, family filtering is applied, removing variants that are present in family members, with heteroplasmy greater than the corresponding heteroplasmy of the proband. At the end of the pipeline, no mitochondrial variant survives (Figure 2, Figure 1).

Since the total number of mitochondrial variants is less than 150, I studied the variants of the proband without any family filtering. I selected only those variants with FILTER = PASS. I then submitted them to the web interface of the mvTool (35), a resource that provides for each variant the population allele frequency, known associations with diseases and phenotypes (from ClinVar, HmtDB, etc.), genomic annotations provided by VEP, computational prediction of pathogenicity by SIFT, PolyPhen, CADD and other in silico methods. After filtering out common and synonymous variants, we remain with 20 calls (Table 14). For CADD scoring, I used the output of CADD v1.3 instead of the one by mvTool. Note that the last version of CADD to support mitochondrial annotation was v1.3. The reference genome was GRCh37, while the reference sequence for the mitochondrial chromosome was rCRS (personal communication by Martin Kircher, one of the current developers of CADD). I

then analyzed in greater detail the variants with a CADD score above 20 (and two other suspect variants) in Table 13. These variants are either at very low heteroplasmy or are present with the same heteroplasmy in the two aunts from the maternal side, therefore, their pathogenicity must be ruled out.

2.4 Generating the joint VCF for structural variants

On Windows Subsystem for Linux (WSL), install bcftools and tabix. Put yourself in the folder where the VCF files are. Then compress them to GZ (if necessary) and add a tabix file for each one. This is an example for the proband:

```
bgzip -c TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra_SV_TOT.vcf> TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra_SV_TOT.vcf.gz
tabix -p vcf TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra_SV_TOT.vcf.gz
```


Figure 1. Filtering of the mitochondrial variants of the proband. Step 1: The initial number of variants. Step 2: quality filtering (only FILTER = PASS and DP>5). Step 3: heteroplasmy filter (only variants with heteroplasmy above 0.2). Step 4-6: family filtering (only variants that are present only in the proband or that are present in the proband with the highest heteroplasmy are kept). Note that at steps 4 and 5, we considered filtering with respect to the two maternal aunts.

Note that the last file is the input. The VCF with all the supplementary samples is necessary only for the proband. For his relatives, we must remove the supplementary samples and then add the tabix file. Here is the syntax for one of the relatives:

```
bcftools view -s TSAA8269 -o TSAA8269_GRCh38_Terra_SV.vcf.gz -O v
TSAA8269_GRCh38_Terra_SV_TOT.vcf.gz
tabix -p vcf TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra_SV.vcf.gz
```

Note that we use the suffix _TOT only for the VCF file that includes all the supplementary samples. Now, to generate the joint VCF, use bcftools with the following syntax:

```
bcftools merge TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra_SV_TOT.vcf.gz TSAA8269_GRCh38_Terra_SV.vcf.gz
TSAB3094_GRCh38_Terra_SV.vcf.gz TSAB3137_GRCh38_Terra_SV.vcf.gz -o
FAM_NuMa_GRCh38_SV_TOT_bcftools.vcf.gz
```


Figure 2. Flowchart for the filtration of proband mitochondrial variants by family filtering.

To use this file in Exomiser, it may be appropriate to keep only the samples that belong to the family of interest. The syntax is:

```
bcftools view -s TSAA1992,TSAA8269,TSAB3094,TSAB3137 -o  
FAM_NuMa_GRCh38_SV_bcftools.vcf.gz -O v FAM_NuMa_GRCh38_SV_TOT_bcftools.vcf.gz
```

2.5 Thresholds used in this pipeline for several in silico scores

We used the thresholds Eigen > 0 and spliceAI > 0.5 for the first screening on Seqr, as detailed in Table 1. Next, Exomiser Pheno score at gene level was used to filter all SNVs/indels, requiring a value ≥ 0.5 . We then used PolyPhen ≥ 0.45 , SIFT ≤ 0.05 , and REVEL ≥ 0.4 for filtering of missense variants. Variants in splice regions were required spliceAI ≥ 0.5 for filtering (this is redundant). As mentioned, SVs were retained only if an ACGM category of at least 3 was assigned by AnnotSV, which corresponds to uncertain significance (US). We also required a combined Exomiser score at gene level ≥ 0.5 for each SV. We used the combined score for SVs to overcome the absence of other in silico filters of pathogenicity.

2.6 Exomiser in standalone execution

The joint VCF file including SNVs/indels and structural variants for the proband and his three relatives was also directly input into Exomiser (release 14.0.0 with data version 2406 and ReMM.v0.3.1). Several combinations of HPO terms were used, and both exome and genome analysis were run. Exomiser was called from a custom R script (ExomiserSolo.R) that also edits, further annotates, and filters Exomiser's output.

To generate the joint VCF for the family of the proband, the following procedure was employed: first, the joint VCF including the SNVs/indels of the four family members plus the 50 samples from the 1000 Genomes Project was edited using package *vcfR* (10) keeping only the four family members. This operation generates file FAM_NuMa_GRCh38_woSV.vcf.gz which includes only the SNVs/indels of the four family members.

Structural variants for the four members were added using bcftools on WSL (to generate a gVCF with SVs only) and then a custom script employing *vcfR*, to merge it with the gVCF generated at previous step. The file resulting from this algorithm is called FAM_NuMa_GRCh38.vcf.gz.

To

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the main steps of the pipeline described in par. 2.2.

Annotation	Source	Ref.
Dosage sensitivity probability	https://zenodo.org/records/6576087	(17)
Probability of a dominant pattern of inheritance (DOMINO score)	https://domino.iob.ch/	(20)
Probability of regulatory features (RegulomeDB)	https://www.regulomedb.org/regulome-search/	(21)
Annotation for non-coding RNA (ncRNAVAR)	http://lilab2.sysu.edu.cn/ncrnavar/Download.jsp	(22)
CADD score (version 1.7)	https://cadd.gs.washington.edu/score	(23)
AMELIE score and papers	https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32434849/	(24)
Gene lists associated with the proband's HPO terms	https://hpo.jax.org/data/annotations	(25)

Table 9. Brief description, sources, and references for the additional annotations to Seqr's output.

File	Format	Depth	Samples	Variant type	Alignment	Edit	Build	Exome	Genome
pam-solo-wes-woMT	vcf	76.7	TSAA1992	SNV	DanteLabs (DRAGEN)		hg19		9 m
FAM_NuMa_GRCh38_woSV	vcf.gz		family NuMa	SNV/indel	Terra (GATK)	VCF_edit.R	hg38	41 h	
TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra_SV_TOT	vcf.gz		157 samples	SV	Terra (GATK)		hg38		
TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra_SV	vcf.gz		TSAA1992	SV	Terra (GATK)	bcftools	hg38		
TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra_AnnotSV	tsv		157 samples	SV	Terra (GATK)	AnnotSV	hg38		
TSAA8269_GRCh38_Terra_SV_TOT	vcf.gz		157 samples	SV	Terra (GATK)		hg38		
TSAA8269_GRCh38_Terra_SV	vcf.gz		TSAA8269	SV	Terra (GATK)	bcftools	hg38		
TSAB3094_GRCh38_Terra_SV_TOT	vcf.gz		157 samples	SV	Terra (GATK)		hg38		
TSAB3094_GRCh38_Terra_SV	vcf.gz		TSAB3094	SV	Terra (GATK)	bcftools	hg38		
TSAB3137_GRCh38_Terra_SV_TOT	vcf.gz		157 samples	SV	Terra (GATK)		hg38		
TSAB3137_GRCh38_Terra_SV	vcf.gz		TSAB3137	SV	Terra (GATK)	bcftools	hg38		
FAM_NuMa_GRCh38	vcf.gz		family NuMa	SNV/indel, SV	Terra (GATK)	SV_edit.R	hg38	42 h	
TSAA1992_GRCh38_Terra	vcf.gz	42.5	TSAA1992	SNV/indel, SV	Terra (GATK)		hg38		22 h
TSAA1992_GRCh38_DL1	vcf.gz	42.5	TSAA1992	SNV/indel, SV	DanteLabs (DRAGEN)		hg38		
TSAA1992_GRCh38_DL2	vcf.gz	42.5	TSAA1992	SNV/indel, CNV	DanteLabs (DRAGEN)		hg38		
TSAA1992_GRCh37_DL	vcf.gz	42.5	TSAA1992	SNV/indel, CNV	DanteLabs (DRAGEN)		hg19		
FAM_NuMa_GRCh38_SV_TOT_bcftools	vcf.gz		160 samples	SV	Terra (GATK)	bcftools	hg38		2 h
FAM_NuMa_GRCh38_SV_bcftools	vcf.gz		family NuMa	SV	Terra (GATK)	bcftools	hg38		
TSAA1992_GRCh37_DL_CNV	vcf.gz		TSAA1992	CNV	DanteLabs (DRAGEN)		hg19		
TSAA1992_GRCh38_DL_CNV	vcf.gz		TSAA1992	CNV	DanteLabs (DRAGEN)		hg38		

Table 10. VCF files used in this study.

Gene	Position on hg38	Position on hg19	R	A	AB	Relatives	Conseq.	Freq.	CADD	Revel	Eigen	Sift	splice AI	ACMG	VS	WES hg19	WGS hg19	MOI	pDI	pHI
LBR	1:225411334	1:225411334	T	C	0.48	N	splice d.	0	16	-	22.2	-	0.73	US	US	Y	Y	AD	0.18	0.87
COL4A4	2:227108582	2:227973298	G	A	0.58	N	miss.	7e-06	26	0.45	5.58	0.014	0.01	US	LP	Y	Y	AD	0.32	0.85
ITGA9	3:37818904	3:37860395	G	A	0.55	N	miss.	4e-04	32	0.41	8.46	0.004	0	US	B	Y	Y	AR	0.52	0.81
CNTN5	11:100299285	11:100170017	C	T	0.55	N	stop g.	0	38	-	6.54	-	0.01	US	LP	Y	Y	AD	0.19	0.42
PRKAB1	12:119672380	12:120110185	C	T	0.58	N	miss.	2e-05	30	0.49	7.49	0.001	0	US	LB	Y	Y	AD	0.36	0.48
GLIPR1	12:75481013	12:75874793	C	T	0.44	N	stop g.	1e-05	39	-	9.64	-	0.02	US	US	Y	Y	AD	0.32	0.19
RECQL	12:21476994	12:21629928	T	C	0.45	N	splice a.	2e-04	27	-	12.15	-	0.87	US	LB	Y	Y	AR	0.46	0.63
TNS2	12:53448166	12:53448166	C	T	0.46	N	miss.	2e-04	28	0.92	4.98	0.001	0	US	US	Y	Y	AD	-	-
CHD9	16:53075340	16:53109252	T	A	0.41	N	intron	0	24	-	0.48	-	0.85	US	LB	Y	Y	AD	0.99	0.99
EPX	17:58199175	17:56276536	G	A	0.37	N	miss.	2e-04	27	0.89	20.51	0.001	0	US	US	Y	Y	AD,AR	0.09	0.22
EPX	17:58195171	17:56272532	G	A	0.61	N	splice d.	2e-03	35	-	14.31	-	1	LB	B	Y	Y	AR	0.09	0.22
ALOX12	17:6996163	17:6899482	T	C	0.46	N	miss.	0	24	0.533	3.70	0.003	0	US	LB	Y	Y	AD	0.08	0.33
GALR3	22:37825087	22:38221094	G	ins	0.53	N	inframe	4e-05	22	-	-	-	-	US	US	Y	Y	AD	0.12	0.36

Table 11. Possible causal SNVs/indels for autosomal dominant pattern of inheritance, de novo, and autosomal recessive. AB: allele balance. ACMG: classification by Exomiser. VS: classification by Varsome. MOI: mode of inheritance as defined by Exomiser. pDI: probability of dominant features according to DOMINO. pHI: probability of haploinsufficiency. WES hg19: is the variant present in WES aligned to GRCh19? WGS hg19: is the variant present in the alignment of WGS raw readings with respect to GRCh19? LP: likely pathogenic. US: uncertain significance. B: benign. LB: likely benign. All these variants are heterozygous in the proband and reference homozygous in his relatives. Freq: allele frequency on Gnomad Genomes.

Gene	Span on hg38	Span	Type	Gen	Consequence	pLoF	pIntro	Freq.	ACMG	VS	ACMG AnnotSV	MOI	pDI	pHI	pTS
TFDP2	3:141999019-141999132	113	DUP	0/1	amplification	-	Y	-	US	US	US	AD	0.81	0.84	0.93
CNTN6	3:1147254-1149203	-1949	DEL	0/1	exon loss	Y	-	-	US	US	US	AD	0.20	0.15	0.05
PCGF6	10:103320759-103320817	58	DUP	1/1	amplification	-	Y	0.18	US	US	US	AR	0.16	0.27	0.42
TYRO3	15:41570155-41570238	-83	DEL	0/1	truncation	-	-	-	US	B	-	AR	0.34	0.37	0.80
TYRO3	15:41570340-41570603	-263	DEL	0/1	truncation	-	-	-	US	US	-	AR	0.34	0.37	0.80
TYRO3	15:41561310-41573307	1706	CPX	0/1	variant	-	-	-	-	-	-	AR	0.34	0.37	0.80
CDH13	16:83398043-83398096	53	DUP	1/1	amplification	-	-	-	US	US	-	AR	0.34	0.84	0.24
PTPRM	18:7916116-7916195	79	DUP	0/1	amplification	-	Y	0.065	US	US	US	AD	0.69	0.98	0.65
HEPH	X:66244543-66279101	34558	DUP	0/1	amplification	-	-	0.0119	US	US	US	XL	-	-	-

Table 12. Possible causal SV. AB: allele balance. ACMG: classification by Exomiser. VS: ACMG classification by Varsome. ACMG AnnotSV: ACMG classification by AnnotSV. MOI: mode of inheritance as defined by Exomiser. pDI: probability of dominant features according to DOMINO. pHI: probability of haploinsufficiency. pTS: probability of Triplosensitivity. pLoF: predicted loss of function. pIntro: predicted intronic. LP: likely pathogenic. US: uncertain significance. B: benign. LB: likely benign.

Variant	Proband HP	Maternal aunt HP	Maternal aunt HP	Paternal uncle HP
m.6692_6692delA	0.0064	-	-	-
m.9531_9532insC	0.0048	-	-	-
m.13227_13228insTACAGCAGTGTGTCAGTGTGCTGTGTGAAGTGTTCGTGT	0.0025	-	-	-
m.13970G>A	0.0082	-	-	-
m.16180_16180delA	0.18	0.16	0.19	-
m.16182_16183insCC	0.12	0.15	0.14	-

Table 13. Selection of variants from Table 14. Heteroplasmy (HP) for the proband and for the relatives (when available) is also reported. When heteroplasmy is not indicated, it means that the sample has the reference genotype at that position.

Variant	AF	Biotype	Consequence	dbSNP	ClinVar	CADD	Impact
m.285C>T	0.0026	coding	upstream gene	rs201801609	-	10.7	MODIFIER
m.2218C>T	0.0019	Mt tRNA	non-coding transcript exon	rs200813159	-	10.96	MODIFIER
m.2746T>C	0.0005	Mt tRNA	non-coding transcript exon	rs28663331	-	9.123	MODIFIER
m.3244G>A	0	Mt tRNA	non-coding transcript exon	-	Uncertain significance	10.35	MODIFIER
m.4412G>A	0.0021	Mt tRNA	non-coding transcript exon	-	-	10.42	MODIFIER
m.6692_6692delA	-	coding	-	rs1569484100	Pathogenic	22.9	HIGH
m.9531_9532insC	-	coding	-	rs267606614	Pathogenic	22	HIGH
m.10203G>A	0.0006	coding	missense	rs1556423781	Benign	7.72	MODERATE
m.13227_13228insTACAGCAGTGTGTCAGTGTGCTGTGTGAAGTGTTCGTGT	-	coding	-	-	-	22.5	HIGH
m.13681A>G	0.004	coding	missense	rs386829187	Benign	1.984	MODERATE
m.13970G>A	0	coding	missense	-	-	23.3	MODERATE
m.14063T>C	0.0004	coding	missense	rs1556424379	Benign	0.015	MODERATE
m.15954A>C	0.0024	coding	upstream gene	rs28561372	-	8.946	MODIFIER
m.16180_16180delA	0.0162	coding	upstream gene	-	Uncertain significance	12.07	MODIFIER
m.16182_16183insCC	0.001	coding	-	-	-	6.283	MODIFIER
m.16249T>C	0.0127	coding	upstream gene	rs372301309	-	10.02	MODIFIER
m.16355C>T	0.0109	coding	upstream gene	rs138576863	-	10.93	MODIFIER
m.16368T>C	0.0041	coding	upstream gene	rs1556424875	-	10.13	MODIFIER
m.16444C>T	0.0001	coding	upstream gene	-	-	11	MODIFIER
m.16527C>T	0.0076	coding	upstream gene	rs370705831	-	11.11	MODIFIER

Table 14. Mitochondrial variants of the proband, after removal of common variants (alternative allele frequency above 0.162). From the output of mvTool. We have FILTER = PASS for all the variants. Six variants of concern are highlighted and further analyzed in Table 13.

3 Results

The result of the pipeline here described, run with eight subgroups of HPO terms from those collected in Table 4, is the set of SNVs/indels and SVs collected in Table 11 and Table 12 respectively. In what follows I present a brief discussion for each item of these tables.

Lamin B-receptor (*LBR*) is one of the lamins, ubiquitous proteins that participate in the mechanical stability of the nucleus. Heterozygous mutations of *LBR* are associated with isolated Pelger-Huët anomaly (PHA), a benign hypolobulation of neutrophil nuclei (36), and possibly to Reynaud syndrome associated with fatigue and primary biliary cirrhosis (PBC) (37). On the other hand, compound heterozygous and homozygous mutations can lead to severe forms of skeletal dysplasia (38). The variant harbored by the proband has not been studied, to our knowledge, and the analysis of structure and shape of his neutrophils is warranted. Despite a low CADD score for this variant, the spliceAI score is suggestive of altered splicing.

COL4A4 encodes collagen type IV alpha 4 chain, one of the six subunits of type IV collagen, a structural protein found only in basement membranes. It is expressed in several tissues, including kidneys, pituitary gland, retina, and skeletal muscles, with low tissue specificity, according to the Human protein Atlas (39) accessed at (<https://www.proteinatlas.org>) on April 2025. The same source, indicates a brain regional enhancement in choroid plexus. Mutations on *COL4A4* are associated with renal diseases, with various degree of severity, from benign familial hematuria to Alport syndrome, a form of progressive renal failure often accompanied by deafness and ocular lesions (40). The trait most frequently associated with this gene on GWAS catalog is systolic blood pressure (studies GCST007267, GCST90292477, and GCST90310294, with p -values below 5×10^{-8} , retrieved from <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gwas/> on April 24, 2025).

ITGA9 encodes for an integrin, a cell surface glycoprotein involved in interactions between cells and interaction between cell and extracellular matrix. It has been linked to systolic blood pressure (41) and to sporadic amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (42).

Gene *CNTN5* encodes a neural adhesion molecule. It belongs to the immunoglobulin superfamily. Common variants of this gene are associated with red cell width variability (43) and volume (44) and with neuroticism (45). In brain, this genes is part of the astrocyte-neuron interaction cluster, according to HPA.

PRKAB1 encodes a regulatory subunit of the AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK), a protein kinase that activates energy-producing pathways and turn off energy-consuming processes, as a response of reduced ATP level (46).

RECQL is a DNA helicase involved in DNA repair. Variants on *RECQL* have been associated with bilirubin level in the UKBiobank database (47). An homozygous mutation on this gene as been associated with progeroid syndrome in three subjects from two unrelated families (48).

EPX encodes for a peroxidase released by eosinophils to mediate lysis of parasites. Homozygous and compound heterozygous mutations on this gene have been associated with Eosinophil peroxidase deficiency, a benign condition (49, 50).

The enzyme encoded by *ALOX12* is thought to regulate platelet function and it is associated with platelet volume in a GWAS study (44).

PCGF56 is expressed in liver, skeletal muscles, and other tissues, with low tissue specificity. It belongs to the liver metabolism gene expression cluster, according to HPA.

4 References

1. Wojcik MH, Reuter CM, Marwaha S, Mahmoud M, Duyzend MH, Barseghyan H, et al. Beyond the exome: what's next in diagnostic testing for Mendelian conditions. ArXiv. United States 2023.
2. Sanchis-Juan A, Stephens J, French CE, Gleadall N, Mégy K, Penkett C, et al. Complex structural variants in Mendelian disorders: identification and breakpoint resolution using short- and long-read genome sequencing. *Genome Med.* 2018;10(1):95.
3. Terra: Broad Institute; 2022 [Available from: <https://app.terra.bio/>].
4. Auwera Gvd, O'Connor BD. *Genomics in the cloud : using Docker, GATK, and WDL in Terra*. First edition. ed. Sebastopol, CA: O'Reilly Media; 2020. xxiv, 467 pages p.
5. bshifaw@broadinstitute.org. Sequence-Format-Conversion [updated 24/06/2022. Available from: <https://app.terra.bio/#workspaces/help-gatk/Sequence-Format-Conversion>].
6. kmathews@broadinstitute.org, svelasqu@broadinstitute.org, tiffanym@broadinstitute.org. GATK-Germline-Preprocessing-For-Variant_Discovery-HG38 [updated 31/03/2023. Available from: <https://app.terra.bio/#workspaces/help-gatk/GATK4-Germline-Preprocessing-VariantCalling-JointCalling>].
7. Auton A, Brooks LD, Durbin RM, Garrison EP, Kang HM, Korbel JO, et al. A global reference for human genetic variation. *Nature.* 2015;526(7571):68-74.
8. svelasqu@broadinstitute.org, bshifaw@broadinstitute.org, cwhelan@broadinstitute.org. GATK-Structural-Variants-Single-Sample [updated 09/02/2023. Available from: <https://app.terra.bio/#workspaces/family-based-WGS/GATK-Structural-Variants-Single-Sample>].
9. Danecek P, Bonfield JK, Liddle J, Marshall J, Ohan V, Pollard MO, et al. Twelve years of SAMtools and BCFtools. *GigaScience.* 2021;10(2).
10. Knaus BJ, Grünwald NJ. vcfr: a package to manipulate and visualize variant call format data in R. *Mol Ecol Resour.* 2017;17(1):44-53.
11. Pais LS, Snow H, Weisburd B, Zhang S, Baxter SM, DiTroia S, et al. seqr: A web-based analysis and collaboration tool for rare disease genomics. *Hum Mutat.* 2022;43(6):698-707.
12. Ionita-Laza I, McCallum K, Xu B, Buxbaum JD. A spectral approach integrating functional genomic annotations for coding and noncoding variants. *Nat Genet.* 2016;48(2):214-20.
13. Li J, Zhao T, Zhang Y, Zhang K, Shi L, Chen Y, et al. Performance evaluation of pathogenicity-computation methods for missense variants. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2018;46(15):7793-804.
14. Human Genome Assembly GRCh38.p14 [updated 2022-02-03. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/grc/human/data>].
15. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria 2024 [Available from: <https://www.R-project.org/>].
16. RStudio: Integrated Development Environment for R. RStudio, PBC, Boston, MA [Available from: <https://posit.co/download/rstudio-desktop/>].
17. Collins RL, Glessner JT, Porcu E, Lepamets M, Brandon R, Lauricella C, et al. A cross-disorder dosage sensitivity map of the human genome. *Cell.* 2022;185(16):3041-55.e25.
18. European Organization For Nuclear R, OpenAire. Zenodo. CERN; 2013.
19. Winter DJ. rentrez: An R package for the NCBI eUtils API. *The R Journal.* 2017;9(2):520-6.

20. Quinodoz M, Royer-Bertrand B, Cisarova K, Di Gioia SA, Superti-Furga A, Rivolta C. DOMINO: Using Machine Learning to Predict Genes Associated with Dominant Disorders. *Am J Hum Genet.* 2017;101(4):623-9.
21. Boyle AP, Hong EL, Hariharan M, Cheng Y, Schaub MA, Kasowski M, et al. Annotation of functional variation in personal genomes using RegulomeDB. *Genome Res.* 2012;22(9):1790-7.
22. Zhang W, Zeng B, Yang M, Yang H, Wang J, Deng Y, et al. ncRNAVar: A Manually Curated Database for Identification of Noncoding RNA Variants Associated with Human Diseases. *J Mol Biol.* 2021;433(11):166727.
23. Kircher M, Witten DM, Jain P, O'Roak BJ, Cooper GM, Shendure J. A general framework for estimating the relative pathogenicity of human genetic variants. *Nat Genet.* 2014;46(3):310-5.
24. Birgmeier J, Haeussler M, Deisseroth CA, Steinberg EH, Jagadeesh KA, Ratner AJ, et al. AMELIE speeds Mendelian diagnosis by matching patient phenotype and genotype to primary literature. *Sci Transl Med.* 2020;12(544).
25. Gargano MA, Matentzoglou N, Coleman B, Addo-Lartey EB, Anagnostopoulos AV, Anderton J, et al. The Human Phenotype Ontology in 2024: phenotypes around the world. *Nucleic Acids Res.* 2024;52(D1):D1333-d46.
26. Thompson R, Papakonstantinou Ntalas A, Beltran S, Töpf A, de Paula Estephan E, Polavarapu K, et al. Increasing phenotypic annotation improves the diagnostic rate of exome sequencing in a rare neuromuscular disorder. *Hum Mutat.* 2019;40(10):1797-812.
27. Jacobsen JOB, Kelly C, Cipriani V, Research Consortium GE, Mungall CJ, Reese J, et al. Phenotype-driven approaches to enhance variant prioritization and diagnosis of rare disease. *Hum Mutat.* 2022;43(8):1071-81.
28. Robinson PN, Köhler S, Oellrich A, Wang K, Mungall CJ, Lewis SE, et al. Improved exome prioritization of disease genes through cross-species phenotype comparison. *Genome Res.* 2014;24(2):340-8.
29. Schubach M, Nazaretyan L, Kircher M. The Regulatory Mendelian Mutation score for GRCh38. *Gigascience.* 2022;12.
30. Jaganathan K, Kyriazopoulou Panagiotopoulou S, McRae JF, Novick PA, Ioannidis NM, Peacock J, et al. Predicting Splicing from Primary Sequence with Deep Learning. *Cell.* 2019;176(3):535-48.e24.
31. Sobreira N, Schiettecatte F, Valle D, Hamosh A. GeneMatcher: a matching tool for connecting investigators with an interest in the same gene. *Hum Mutat.* 2015;36(10):928-30.
32. Sturm M, Kleinheinz K, Schmutz J, Stütz AM. Adding AnnotSV in your SV annotation workflow. *Frontiers in Genetics.* 2023;14.
33. Poulos RC, Wong JWH, Ryan J, Pang H, Murigneux V. AnnotSV v2.0: characterization and functional annotation of structural variations. *NAR Genomics and Bioinformatics.* 2022;4(3):lqac059.
34. Geoffroy V, Herenger Y, Kress A, Stoetzel C, Piton A, Dollfus H, et al. AnnotSV: an integrated tool for structural variations annotation. *Bioinformatics.* 2018;34(20):3572-4.
35. Shen L, Attimonelli M, Bai R, Lott MT, Wallace DC, Falk MJ, et al. MSeqDR mvTool: A mitochondrial DNA Web and API resource for comprehensive variant annotation, universal nomenclature collation, and reference genome conversion. *Hum Mutat.* 2018;39(6):806-10.
36. Best S, Salvati F, Kallo J, Garner C, Height S, Thein SL, et al. Lamin B-receptor mutations in Pelger-Huët anomaly. *Br J Haematol.* 2003;123(3):542-4.
37. Gaudy-Marqueste C, Roll P, Esteves-Vieira V, Weiller PJ, Grob JJ, Cau P, et al. LBR mutation and nuclear envelope defects in a patient affected with Reynolds syndrome. *J Med Genet.* 2010;47(6):361-70.
38. Giorgio E, Sirchia F, Bosco M, Sobreira NLM, Grosso E, Brussino A, et al. A novel case of Greenberg dysplasia and genotype-phenotype correlation analysis for LBR pathogenic variants: An instructive example of one gene-multiple phenotypes. *Am J Med Genet A.* 2019;179(2):306-11.

39. Uhlén M, Fagerberg L, Hallström BM, Lindskog C, Oksvold P, Mardinoglu A, et al. Tissue-based map of the human proteome. *Science*. 2015;347(6220):1260419.
40. Mencarelli MA, Heidet L, Storey H, van Geel M, Knebelmann B, Fallerini C, et al. Evidence of digenic inheritance in Alport syndrome. *J Med Genet*. 2015;52(3):163-74.
41. Keaton JM, Kamali Z, Xie T, Vaez A, Williams A, Goleva SB, et al. Genome-wide analysis in over 1 million individuals of European ancestry yields improved polygenic risk scores for blood pressure traits. *Nat Genet*. 2024;56(5):778-91.
42. Xie T, Deng L, Mei P, Zhou Y, Wang B, Zhang J, et al. Genome-wide association study combining pathway analysis for typical sporadic amyotrophic lateral sclerosis in Chinese Han populations. *Neurobiol Aging*. 2014;35(7):1778.e9-.e23.
43. Chen MH, Raffield LM, Mousas A, Sakaue S, Huffman JE, Moscati A, et al. Trans-ethnic and Ancestry-Specific Blood-Cell Genetics in 746,667 Individuals from 5 Global Populations. *Cell*. 2020;182(5):1198-213.e14.
44. Vuckovic D, Bao EL, Akbari P, Lareau CA, Mousas A, Jiang T, et al. The Polygenic and Monogenic Basis of Blood Traits and Diseases. *Cell*. 2020;182(5):1214-31.e11.
45. Baselmans BML, Jansen R, Ip HF, van Dongen J, Abdellaoui A, van de Weijer MP, et al. Multivariate genome-wide analyses of the well-being spectrum. *Nat Genet*. 2019;51(3):445-51.
46. Sanz P. AMP-activated protein kinase: structure and regulation. *Curr Protein Pept Sci*. 2008;9(5):478-92.
47. Sinnott-Armstrong N, Tanigawa Y, Amar D, Mars N, Benner C, Aguirre M, et al. Genetics of 35 blood and urine biomarkers in the UK Biobank. *Nat Genet*. 2021;53(2):185-94.
48. Abu-Libdeh B, Jhujh SS, Dhar S, Sommers JA, Datta A, Longo GM, et al. RECON syndrome is a genome instability disorder caused by mutations in the DNA helicase RECQL1. *J Clin Invest*. 2022;132(5).
49. Romano M, Patriarca P, Melo C, Baralle FE, Dri P. Hereditary eosinophil peroxidase deficiency: immunochemical and spectroscopic studies and evidence for a compound heterozygosity of the defect. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*. 1994;91(26):12496-500.
50. Nakagawa T, Ikemoto T, Takeuchi T, Tanaka K, Tanigawa N, Yamamoto D, et al. Eosinophilic peroxidase deficiency: Identification of a point mutation (D648N) and prediction of structural changes. *Hum Mutat*. 2001;17(3):235-6.